

Practical lessons in building collaborative science platforms with open-source tools

Hubert Siejkowski, Tomasz Balawajder, Maciej Leśniak, Joanna Kocot, Krystyna Milian, Jakub Sto, and Bartłomiej Wenda

Academic Computer Centre CYFRONET of the AGH University of Krakow, Krakow, Poland; hubert.siejkowski@cyfronet.pl

Abstract.

Advanced science platforms must handle large data volumes, complex workflows, and collaborations that span multiple disciplines and partners. While scientific questions may differ between fields, the challenges of building reliable and reproducible data-driven research infrastructures are very similar.

We show how a geophysics-oriented science platform integrates well known open-source services to support the full lifecycle of data-intensive research. The platform consists of monitoring, log aggregation and analysis tools. These tools provide real-time insights into the health and efficiency of the platform and scientific workflows. They are also generating metrics and usage reports that satisfy accountability requirements of funding agencies.

Beyond infrastructure monitoring, collaboration and reproducibility are enabled through distributed version control, allowing users to develop and run custom applications on our platform. To support the increasing role of machine learning in scientific workflows, we integrate tools for experiment tracking, model management and collaborative dataset curation and annotation. The platform supports execution on remote workers and HPC clusters, enabling scalable computation and flexible integration with existing research infrastructures.

Our experience demonstrates that combining these tools into a modular ecosystem creates science platforms that are scalable, and cultivate reproducibility. Key lessons stress the need to balance automation with researcher control, design platforms that enable cross-disciplinary collaboration, and adopt testing frameworks to ensure platform reliability. Although developed for geophysics, this approach is directly transferable to astrophysics and other data-intensive fields.

1. Introduction

The Episodes Platform¹ is a collaborative research platform for conducting research in geophysics (Orlecka-Sikora et al. 2020). The platform focuses on anthropogenic seismology, which deals with seismic activity caused by human activity, such as mining or reservoir impoundment. The development of the platform is a collaboration between ACC Cyfronet AGH and the Institute of Geophysics Polish Academy of Sciences, combining expertise in IT and geophysics, respectively.

¹<https://EpisodesPlatform.eu>

The Episodes Platform is one of the Thematic Core Services with the European Plate Observing System² (EPOS). EPOS is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) that serves as a multidisciplinary, distributed network. Its purpose is to facilitate the integrated use of data, data products, and facilities from the solid Earth science community across Europe.

Target users are students, lecturers, and entry- and mid-level scientists. The main functionality of the Episodes Platform is to simplify data selection and perform subsequent analysis steps. Users can create workflows and reuse them in the future, allowing for a streamlined analysis process. Workflows can be shared between users and developed jointly. Users can also develop their own applications and use them in data analysis or even share them with the entire user community.

2. Aims of the Episodes Platform

The primary objectives of the Episodes Platform are to enhance research in anthropogenic seismology by providing an integrated environment for data analysis, workflow creation, and resource sharing. The typical user scenario using the platform is as follows:

Find and select data. Data storage systems are distributed and hosted by different institutions. The Episodes Platform provides a frontend for accessing these systems, allowing users to browse the data, select it, and attach it to their user workspace. The download process runs behind the scenes. Each data set is assigned a data type, which is helpful in later steps.

Run applications. The applications can be run using the downloaded data as an input. The user can upload their own data as well. The assigned data types (described in the previous step) are used to limit the selection of applications suggested by the system, since each data type has a list of applications that can process it.

Create custom applications. In the case if the selection of prebuilt applications is too restrictive, the user can create their own applications and execute them on the platform. A custom application must provide the list of data types that it can process and the list of outputs (including their data types). The development of a custom application can be done on the platform. It is possible to develop a custom application in a local development environment and then upload any working version to the platform.

Join application into workflows. Individual applications can be organized into workflows that can combine each analysis step into a single executable workflow. The workflows take a list of inputs that represents the combined set of inputs required by each application within the workflow. The outputs comprise all of the outputs generated by each application.

Collaboration. Each folder containing applications, together with its inputs and outputs, as well as the workflows, can be shared with a selected group of collaborators. The shared resources can be further developed by those users.

²<https://www.epos-eu.org>

3. Internals of the Episodes Platform

The platform consists of a distributed set of tools that are connected to the central web portal. The web portal, which is the heart of the system, is a Java application built with the Google Web Toolkit³ (GWT). This portal hosts the user workspace and governs the computations. The persistence of the system is supported by a MongoDB database (Sholmes et al. 2023) which stores information about the user profile and workspace. The data files used by the users in their analysis are kept on the local filesystem; files exceeding a size threshold are sent to an object storage backed by the S3 Ceph Object Gateway service.

Authorization and authentication (AA) are crucial due to the distributed nature of the Episodes Platform. The service driving our AA is Unity IdM⁴, which implements the OpenID Connect standard (Gupta 2024). This enables users to log into all tools using a single set of credentials, eliminating repeated logins and password fatigue in a Single Sign-On (SSO) model.

One of the core functionalities of the platform is to run applications that perform scientific analysis tasks. To move the computations off the platform, we introduced a system of workers that are responsible for fetching the input data, performing the computations, and sending back the results. The workers are Java services that can be run on any machine but require a connection to the task queue. The task queue is managed by an ActiveMQ instance (Snyder et al. 2011). Tasks can differ in their input size and the required computing resources; therefore, the platform supports two types of tasks: simple and intensive. The simple tasks are routed to workers that are constantly online, and they process the arriving tasks almost instantly. More intensive tasks are run on a remote HPC cluster. Connection to the cluster is via the SSH gateway, which allows the platform to submit SLURM jobs (Yoo et al. 2003). A worker is started within the SLURM job and processes tasks from the task queue. In this setup, the worker can run computationally intensive tasks, which require greater memory and multiple CPU cores.

The applications run by the workers are predefined in the Episodes Platform; however, users can also create their own custom applications. The Application Workbench is an instance of Gitea (a Git hosting platform) integrated into the Episodes Platform. The workers download the custom application automatically via the REST API, without user interaction. The only requirement on the worker side is the local installation of the necessary software or library dependencies. Workers support running applications written in Python, R, Octave, Matlab, or bash scripts.

For the Python custom applications, environment requirements can be defined in the source code repository, as the worker has built-in support for the Micromamba environments. In this case, the worker fetches the source code and creates the Python environment based on the provided definition before running the application. This allows users to easily incorporate any libraries required to perform their analysis tasks.

From the perspective of platform maintainers and managers, tools have been developed to monitor both the current status and health of the system and measure and collect usage metrics. The metrics are used in reports to stakeholders, demonstrating

³<https://www.gwtproject.org>

⁴<https://unity-idm.eu>

that the Episodes Platform has a growing user base and is actively used by the community. From the developers' point of view, the metrics are very helpful for understanding how users interact with the platform and for identifying potential problems. For example, the metrics are used to estimate the runtime of a given application to determine whether it should be submitted to the HPC cluster because its potential runtime is too long for the workers assigned to the simple tasks.

The collection of the metrics from the systems is performed with the aid of Prometheus and Flunetd. The first tool is responsible for collecting the metrics from monitoring agents, while the second collects log entries from multiple sources and aggregates them into a single database. To explore the collected monitoring entries, we use Grafana. Log entries are aggregated into a database powered by Elasticsearch with a user-friendly front end powered by Kibana. On a daily basis, the collected log entries are scanned for potential errors. If any are detected, an alert is sent to the monitoring team. The alerting system is based on Alertmanager and ElastAlert.

4. Summary

From more than ten years of experience developing the platform, we have identified the following key points: (1) The complex research platform for a specific domain can be implemented using open-source tools. Building on open-source tools and standards ensures interoperability, eases maintenance, and prevents vendor lock-in, which is critical for long-term research infrastructure; (2) Many open-source solutions need only slight modifications to meet the requirements of scientific research problems, and additional integration logic is necessary to connect these tools into a unified platform; (3) Implementing a robust Single Sign-On system is crucial; (4) Close collaboration between developers and researchers with expertise in the domain is essential; (5) Comprehensive monitoring of the system provides significant benefits for both users and platform managers; (6) The architecture of such a platform must be designed for adaptability and be ready to meet future demands.

Acknowledgments. This work is co-financed from the program of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education "Supporting the participation of Polish research teams in international research infrastructure projects" (D-UMO-33/24) and EPOS ON by the EC Horizon Europe programme under G.A. n101131592. We gratefully acknowledge Polish high-performance computing infrastructure PLGrid (HPC Center: ACK Cyfronet AGH) for providing computer facilities and support within computational grant no. PLG/2025/018833 and PLG/2025/01884.

References

- Gupta, A. 2024, IDPro Body of Knowledge, 1. URL <https://doi.org/10.55621/idpro.109>
- Orlecka-Sikora, B., Lasocki, S., Kocot, J., Szepieniec, T., Grasso, J. R., Garcia-Aristizabal, A., Schaming, M., Urban, P., Jones, G., Stimpson, I., & et al. 2020, *Scientific Data*, 7, 89
- Sholmes, E., Chodorow, K., & DiGiano, D. 2023, *MongoDB: The Definitive Guide* (Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media), 3rd ed.
- Snyder, B., Bosanac, D., & Davies, R. 2011, *ActiveMQ in Action* (Manning)
- Yoo, A. B., Jette, M. A., & Grondona, M. 2003, in *Job Scheduling Strategies for Parallel Processing*, edited by D. Feitelson, L. Rudolph, & U. Schwiegelshohn (Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg), 44